

**Where the World ‘shatters’?
Some reflections on geopolitics of mobilities in
the contemporary world**

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Abstract:

The aim of this contribution is to visit a debate, presenting some questions for discussion and exchange. It does not pretend to be a lecture, or to answer questions about contemporary geopolitics. Furthermore, it pretends to be a medium to discuss some political assumptions and social practices that may help to understand the socio-spatial configuration of present and future world politics.

In that way, I will start by locating this text theoretically, followed by some general readings on the geopolitical context. One of the challenges underlined in the contemporary geopolitics, that of mobilities, will be addressed in the COVID 19 and Russia-Ukraine war general scenario, in order to think how the making of geopolitical communities is tangled to the normality/exceptionality approach to mobilities.

Key words:

geopolitics, mobilities, containment of mobility, COVID-19

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Introduction

This manuscript is part of a geopolitical reading, that is, a spatial approach to power relations at the global scale. These power relations mark and define international space. And even today, to talk of Geopolitics as a field of research remains relatively controversial; precisely, because of the associations between the practice of geopolitics and various political projects and intellectual influences; from Ratzel's spatial determinism to the *Geopolitik* of Haushofer and the Institute for Geopolitical Studies in Munich, passing by Augusto Pinochet's Alpaca plan or the geopolitics of a militarized globalization of Thomas Barnett (Lois 2022, 5-6).

However, the use of geopolitics to justify political projects or to argue about hegemonic ways of seeing the world does not invalidate its object of study, nor does it weaken its transcendence, nor, above all, its tradition as an academic discipline. In any case, the differences in the conceptual definition of the term are precisely one of the keys to understanding the constant renewal of the discipline. So, geopolitics here is assumed as a re-reading, a re-visioning of the arguments, visions and geographical practices on which the space of world politics is performed and reproduced.

Now, the spatial part in the concept of geopolitics would not be equivalent to generate an instruction manual on how to dominate a space; or to understand space as a passive and static element of world politics; or as the support for a political project. But as a discursive field where the meanings of space are constructed from the political, academic, popular or any other plane of representation. Without ceasing to work with the arguments and logics of the elites, approaches to other hierarchies, other institutionalities, other voices allow us to question binary geographies, and open debates on power relations assumed as perpetual or introduce multiscale perspectives in a field that cyclically hatches to the rhythm of global upheavals. And, precisely for this reason, asking questions about what is assumed as global from different spaces, scales, networks, agencies... or working with everyday practices and representations and with the possible lines of escape that this allows are still absolutely necessary exercises (Lois 2022, 6).

The 'Shattering' Context

Understanding geopolitics as a discursive field, then, speaks to us of plans of representation and power relations in the production of that global scale. And questions as the COVID-19 pandemics in 2020, or the war between Russia and Ukraine bring attention to the cyclical changes and 'shattering' processes that renew understandings and assumptions underpinning the modern geopolitical imagination (Agnew 2005). Those may be read as symptoms, not as causes, of a multidimensional crisis with diverse aspects already started in the 2000's first decade.

The financial one, in 2008-2009, when the bank system breakdown affected the core and periphery states, pointing to the shrinking of the world GDP around 3% by the end of 2009, with the core countries suffering a reduction of almost 4%, while periphery countries slowed their growth to just under 4% per year (IMF 2023).

The eco-social crises, or the evidence that contemporary capitalism is not compatible with ecology and sustainability. Climate emergency and global warming are key in the creation of the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, UN), the 2030 agenda etc. But these developments and other international and global governance organizations are questioned, by their unequal reactions to the regression in rights and democracies, to war conflicts and inequality persisting in the global South.

The COVID 19 pandemics, an unprecedented crisis that defined global health crisis of our time, since it affected every continent (except Antarctica), in diverse manners. Starting in 2019 December, officially proclaimed by WHO (World Health Organization) in 2020 and ended in 2023, it shows an unofficial date of 20-30 millions of people deaths that underline, in an overwhelming manner, the social determinants of health and the pandemic's impact.

The military crisis, today centered in the war between Russia and Ukraine, probably because of European location and implication in the conflict. Some other continue (Yemen, Afghanistan, South Sudan etc.) out of the media and general attention. There is nothing inevitable in the outbreaks of war; unfortunately, they are not anomalies, burdens of the past but continuation of conflicts acquiring a war moment, final expression of scale practices in social and political constructions of the enemy, with a militaristic but also patriarchal background: as Eliane Brum wrote "this is another war of white men clinging to the past and their patriarchal values [...] while the world is configured by the carbon economy" (El País 2022). Militarization and belligerence have continuity on various scales, from the culture of cancellation in various events and academic circles, to the daily personalization of the enemy in nationalities, social psychologies and even meals that derive in the emotional demonization of the Other. All this complicates the possibility of contemplating other logics to resolve conflicts, which are certainly minimal.

These generally addressed contemporary dynamics set the scope to think about the world to come, not forgetting the necessary long perspective to think about global change but acknowledging this interregnum (Babic 2020) or liminal time (García Linera 2021).

Global health, food security, climate emergency, or human mobilities, have become essential challenges for contemporary geopolitics.

In that sense, open the lens to look to different regions may be a pattern to approach and discuss taken-for granted views and perceptions, from different planes of production of the global geopolitical imagination. In times of shattering, we may also interrogate and contemplate other dynamics that may highlight different tendencies and transformations or continuities in terms of responses to global

changes. For example, in times and terms of COVID 19, the other face of the coin was the creation or reactivation of mutual popular support networks. In the Brazilian Amazonia, in Bolivian highlands, or in Madrid some examples of this common dynamic featured the social construction of responses to exceptional times (Pachaguayaya & Terrazas 2021; Lois & González-Iturraspe 2021). When thinking about food sovereignty, the conformation of an international social movement also scores the articulation of global responses from locality experiences (see, e.g., International Movement for Food Sovereignty 2023). Another reading of the climate change policies, published in Foreign Policy, speaks about climate colonialism and green capitalism in the global South (Ramachandran 2021), and an eco-social and intercultural pact of the South is proposing frames to cope with the contemporary context in Latin America (Eco social and Intercultural Pact of the South 2020). Proposals such as the New Social Contract (Common Action Forum 2023) or demonstrations for peace in Europe scarcely visible in European media (Stop War 2023) wave the making of spaces for other geopolitical imaginations of the political community limits and central values. In sum, diverse voices seem to open answers of practices to outlook the world to come. Avoiding generalizations but also exceptionalisms, normal and exceptional practices and central political spaces in crisis times are projected and performed in many different forms.

In the next pages, addressing more specifically one of these challenges, that of human mobility in times of crisis will be an excuse to open a conversation around the social construction of normality (and exceptionality) for the daily contemporary geopolitics. Thinking about the delimitation of spaces and ways to manage who is in and out of the political community may be a fruitful exercise to find a vanishing point in thinking about global change.

Mobility, displacement, transit, movement²

Migration, understood as displacement, as the temporary or permanent mobility of people and/or groups, would seem to be consubstantial to the history of humanity. To the global history of humanity, so to speak. We were told that human beings moved, already in prehistoric times, and this is what we have learned. They moved in search of a better life, whatever the meaning of that adjective, which could range from having access to more food to a context of life projected as more favorable, in material, climatic, socio-environmental, affective, or any other possible terms; even none of them. In this sense, mobility and migrations are part of the social, in general, of how what we understand as social happens, and of how the communities themselves are defined, of which the people who move are part, regardless of their legal status. Rather than thinking of these mobilities as an external element, as an externally constituent other of these communities, migration and the ways of practicing movement and mobility shape social formation.

² A first version of the reflections to come was published in *Metápolis* as “Movilidades e (in)seguridades: de las políticas de vigilancia a las políticas de compasión” (Lois 2022).

However, in recent decades, especially in the last decade, a connection between mobility and (in)security has become stronger, imagining borders as devices for territorial control of mobility. Moments such as 9/11, the "cayuco crisis", the "Arab spring", the "long summer of migration" (also known as the refugee crisis) ... have become references of how this security-mobility nexus has been gaining centrality in the social imagination, performed from the constant demarcation of its limits, and practiced through its delimitation, in different times and spaces.

Surveillance and compassion

It does not seem that obstacles to mobility manage to slow or prevent migration. Neither in terms of border security, nor in terms of mobility-controlling technology, does a causal relationship emerge between the two. Granted, these obstacles transform migration routes and timescales, but they do not prevent borders from being crossed; in fact, paradoxically, some of the most heavily policed borders are also those which are most frequently crossed. However, these measures do play a role in strengthening the perception of the threat posed by movement, as well as the territorial effectiveness of these containment measures. They are part of a performance in which the obstacles play a key role in portraying movement as unsafe and threatening, but this dynamic is caught between two things: self-referential and effective territorial political practices with insecurity looming on the horizon, and possible cartographies which reflect social movements whose aim is to go beyond the territorial. In the same way, a whole political economy of migration has been generated around these movements, and it is a topic that has generated a growing amount of research in a number of different areas. It is not only people or groups who are in motion, but also various organizations, institutions, resources, laws, and so on. We are not only referring here to physical journeys, but also to elements of the projection, construction and reproduction of migratory situations and contexts, with little attention to the political condition of vulnerability engendered by mobility. Thus, migrants' situations are affected not only by obstacles and limitations, but also by the organizations, institutions, resources and rights involved in their movement. These can be at the origin of their journeys, at a temporary or permanent destination and, ultimately, in the very concept of mobility, which is rarely if ever perceived as a process with any degree of autonomy, more often being characterized by an assistance-focused approach.

Considering this, it may be valuable to see things from a different perspective. In this case one that highlights the strong contrast between both narratives, perceptions and data, surrounding the movement of people, which is a tremendously fertile area from which to explore the practices of control over mobility. The media summarizes migration at the southern border of Spain, and therefore at the southern edge of Europe itself, with images of 150 sub-Saharan men clambering or jumping over a wire fence. This portrayal is in stark contrast with the acknowledgement in reports by the European Commission that the majority of what are termed "irregular migrants" initially access the Schengen area via regular, legal

means by obtaining a non-permanent visa, but then fail to leave when their visas expire (European Commission 2020; Krotký & Kaniok 2020). The fact was also referenced on maps of migratory patterns published by Frontex on their old website and in other publications on risk analysis, as well as in academic work that has been widely read and referenced; all this is to say that these issues are institutionally recognized and have been the topic of debate. The contrast between different narratives indicates a certain level of exceptionality attached to certain movements, rooted in references to ideas of race, gender and criminalized forms of movement, from which large-scale policies are put into action to identify and control migration. The resulting vision boils down to the surveillance of foreign citizens who enter Europe with a likelihood of staying illegally, having crossed its borders in a *violent* and *disorderly* manner.

On the other hand, institutionally confirmed figures point towards a need for new perspectives on how migration is viewed. Returning to the context of Spain, the figures from the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE, *Instituto Nacional de Estadística*) for the first half of 2022 established that migratory flows came from Morocco, Romania, Colombia, the United Kingdom, Italy and Venezuela, in that order. This essentially means that they come from a neighboring country in North Africa, members or former members of the European Union, and Latin America. Once again, exploring the contrast between rhetoric and reality can prove a thought-provoking exercise; think of how British or Italian citizens factor into this collective imagining of migration, or property investors, or applicants for so-called “citizenship by investment” (in Spanish CIP, *Ciudadanía por Inversión*), or members of the armed forces, to name but a few. It would appear that there is a lucid and clear abstraction of what constitutes a migrant, what their problems might be, their possible agendas and their position in society in terms of assistance or intervention needed to avoid exclusion (Colectivo IOE 2010; Ribas-Mateos 2018).

In the Other Spaces: some every-day making of exceptionality

In the year 2015, during the “long summer of migration”, when people were moving through Europe on foot in search of a temporary or permanent home, there were many experiences which I believe may help us to reflect about the everyday dynamics and spaces which reproduce and create inequality. However, we will focus on one of these experiences which is of particular interest to scholars of movement and borders. At Radboud University in Nijmegen, on the border between Germany and The Netherlands, a group of colleagues associated with the internationally renowned Nijmegen Centre for Border Research (NCBR) began an informal initiative which they named Asylum University. Under this title, they organized opportunities specifically for asylum seekers, which included guaranteed access to university education, arranging talks, debates and language classes. This initiative is central in the dissertation thesis of Kolar Aparna (2020), graduate student at the NCBR, embracing how the spirit of the project was to provide a space for everyday events related to teaching and research, through which connections could be formed

between spaces of knowledge exchange and temporary accommodation—i.e., shelters, refugee centers and the University—and in this way create safe places for collective action and reflection. Shortly after its inception, one of the Netherlands' emergency shelters was opened close to the campus, housing around 3000 people opposite the main university community offices. In spite of the difficulties experienced by the initiative it managed, at least temporarily, to shake up people's previously held notions around migration, migrant spaces, and socially expected or accepted forms of residence. Aparna (2020) lists some exchanges with academic experts in border studies and administrative personnel that reveal a fear of engaging with people who have some form of unregulated status, as well as an inability to involve with asylum seekers on a level beyond mere academic consideration. They are considered to be objects of study, always in some space of waiting for a status, but maybe never sharing that which is understood to be the same as our own.

Around that time several similar initiatives were proposed in universities in Spain, with varying degrees of acceptance. In addition to Spain's migrant intake numbers being undeniably lower than those of countries such as Germany or the Netherlands, the initiatives failed to make much of an impact in an administrative, bureaucratic and academic landscape which believed it had already pinned down the problems (and solutions) of such a group. In many instances, the opening up of public spaces such as classrooms and University facilities for in-person, non-hierarchical social interaction was dismissed on grounds of security, citing possible disagreements and conflicts. The discomfort caused by an unregulated gathering which occurred outside the confines of preconceived expectations around the vulnerability of those who migrate and the help they receive demonstrates how complex perspectives on (some types of) migration can be. At the same time, this also highlights the disruptive potential of opening up every day social spaces, something that the hosts intended as a means, rather than an end in itself. Universities, as public spaces with a social function, are places for social change, and the ingenuousness of these proposals may well be a vital and powerful strategy if we are to continue thinking about the possibility of emancipating our gaze on mobilities, migration and movement.

It is precisely in the places where mobility and migration are researched, in public and in publicly acknowledged spaces of equal conditions, that the possibility of other kinds of encounters may be envisaged. If this does not prove true then, at least as Aparna implies, they can serve as places to reflect on the environment and sense of community of universities as a subject to be studied in itself, given that they do in fact create differences and inequalities. Despite the possible difficulties, I would also like to think that, in the immediacy and closeness of everyday life, the relationships we establish are complex, but also open and malleable, with the potential to free us from narrow, fixed perspectives on migration. Conflict is just as much a part of society as agreement, and it is much easier to resolve and explore it in relatively informal spaces that are free from regulation or interference. Therefore, it is by living among one another that we can finally find somewhere to explore both

conflict and agreement, and we must ultimately remember that diversity is not exclusive to populations in movement.

The territorial trap

Looking beyond the ingenuousness of the previous paragraphs, another important point to be made about the link between migration and (in)security is its territorial manifestations, which made a brief appearance at the beginning of the text in our discussion of the systematic recourse to territorial solutions for dealing with possible threats, specifically the building of border walls. The idea of creating a physical barrier between nations is, of course, nothing new—on the contrary, it is ontologically tied to the construction of the modern nation-state. However, it is worth noting that interest in them has reached a fever pitch in recent years in spite of their questionable efficacy. Elizabeth Vallet (2022) recounts how the existence of such walls has grown from 15 in 1989 to 74 in 2022, with at least 15 more at the planning stage. Her research relates this to the end of the Cold War, and then later to 9/11, arguing that the COVID-19 pandemic consolidated the trend towards the development and installation of physical infrastructure as the central component of a hermetically sealed border. In the context of the European Union, requests for financing to build border security infrastructure have been growing over time. At almost the same time as the implementation of the Temporary Protection Directive for people coming from Ukraine, the militarization and construction of a fence by Poland on its border with Belarus and the construction of another wall on its border with Russia in Kaliningrad clearly demonstrated the differentiated treatment for migrants depending on their supposed points of origin and subsequent political practices or beliefs. In public rhetoric on the matter, and in a letter to the European Commission, which was signed by 12 ministries of member states, attention was drawn to the “need to adapt the existing legal framework to the new realities, enabling us to adequately address attempts of instrumentalization of illegal migration for political purposes and other hybrid threats” (Politico 2021,1). The idea that certain types of migration can be saved by building walls to block other types of migration is paradoxical, to say the very least.

As Vallet notes, the COVID-19 pandemic brought certain trends in the relationship between migration and (in)security into focus. On the European stage, the decision was made for the first time to close external borders on 17 March 2020. In the weeks leading up to this closure, the connection between mobility, security and the pandemic had already been making its presence known on various parts of the global stage, in different to political leaders in Europa, such as Hungarian prime minister: “Because movement spreads the disease and makes the epidemic global, and migration is movement, therefore there is a logical link between the two [...] Hungary has managed to defend against migration, so we are protected against the infections migrants may bring with them” (Dunai 2020). In other words, what can be found outside the border may not stay put, and if it gets in, problems will only increase. This gestures to disease as something tied to place, meaning the antidote

to it is, consequently, a territorial matter (Lois 2020, 295). The border can therefore erase the very question of whether sick (or healthy) people exist, as it provides a line which divides sick people or carriers of disease from the healthy; in this particular case, it excluded anyone and everyone outside the country.

With the borders closed, the only permitted movement was that of goods and journeys considered essential to the continued functioning of shared territory. The request for coordination in communications from the European Commission firmly establishes the link between borders and security by creating an area where “the EU’s external border has to act as a security perimeter for all Schengen States” (European Commission 2020).

It is interesting to remark that EU interstate borders close on a relatively continuous basis in the presence of so-called “exceptional circumstances”. The Schengen Borders Code has always permitted the introduction of controls at its internal borders on the basis of such exceptional circumstances, as dictated by Chapter II of Regulation UE2016/399 which was reformed in 2016, in particular articles 25 and 30. In fact, *exceptional circumstances* have ranged from sporting events to Pope visits, G-7 meetings, NATO and climate summits, terrorist attacks, political protests or Hell’s Angels gatherings (Lois 2014). In COVID 19 times, the pandemic has led at least 14 countries (Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Germany, Estonia, Portugal, Spain, Finland, Belgium, Switzerland and Norway) to strengthen their internal EU borders as a way to control the movement of people, with those of Germany, Austria, Denmark, France, Norway and Sweden being maintained in more or less the same conditions since the refugee crisis of 2015.

The generalization of restrictions on mobility in the context of COVID-19, on the other hand, can also allow for reflection on how immobility has come to be a strategy in the establishment of security. In a time of widespread restriction of movement, the irrelevance of spaces normally used to impose immobility and isolation were resoundingly revealed to be just another territorial tool for maintaining certain movement and security under *normal* circumstances. This was demonstrated as soon as these places where control of movement was exercised within the European Union became affected by the pandemic. For example, in Spain on 6 May 2020, the eight functioning Migrant Detention Centers (known in Spanish by the acronym CIE: *Centro de Internamiento de Extranjeros*), were closed. [9] These centers, originally conceived in 1986 as non-penitentiary facilities in which to hold migrants for a maximum of 60 days while they were in the process of being deported, are a product of the first Spanish Immigration Law on the rights and liberties of foreign nationals (*Ley Orgánica 7/1985 sobre Derechos y Libertades de los Extranjeros*). The suspension of administrative timeframes and processes, as well as flights (including repatriation flights), made it impossible to formalize deportation. It is interesting to note how the immobility of some turns out to be the mobility of others. Much like in other spaces which are intended to safeguard the movement of some by restricting that of others (CIEs, refugee camps, prisons), once movement was restricted in general, immobility and isolation ceased to be *convenient*. Restrictions

on mobility enable other forms of mobility which, in this case paradoxically became a strategy for survival. In short, the territorial trap, whereby different visions of spatial socialization become entangled, is of utmost significance; it points towards a territorial imaginary in which controlling mobility means that, by closing the borders, you limit danger, movement and exceptionality. Nevertheless, it was precisely this exceptionality that showed mobility to be a key element of how society is formed, how it is an integral part of the world economy, and that it is crucial to the maintenance of the labor activities needed to reproduce the system itself.

Throughout this complex rhetorical landscape, public policy conception and management plays a fundamental role. Decisions about rights, controls, interventions and, ultimately, what constitutes the legitimate movement of people all form part of the institutional framework and of the decisions institutionally taken at every possible level. Here, again, we can see how society starts with the establishment of free movement as a human right, as stated in, for example, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms. Such a right undeniably exists to ensure diversity without threatening national unity, but it ultimately amounts to an explicit protection of the right to movement within society.

Approaching now another crisis, that is, the war in Ukraine, we also find another context to think about how the approach to movement and mobility within a community underlines the limits of the (geo)political common space. In March 2022, the European Union activated the Temporary Protection Directive (TPD), which granted immediate protection for one year to those fleeing the war in Ukraine, including Ukrainian nationals, third countries nationals, stateless people and legal residents in the country. This protection granted residency permits, the ability to work, access to medical care, and so on. This directive, though created in 2001, was not put into action in 2015 during the Syrian War. Only in 2022 was it first implemented, when it showcased the efficient, effective and organized provision of asylum and protection based on certain universal rights. However, the impact on institutions and groups involved in previous movements has become evident, and thus decisions made by institutions at various levels—which have not been extended to others in similar circumstances—uphold inequalities, establish preferential treatment for legitimate or related migratory flows and, lastly, uphold the material and symbolic conditions which underpin this mindset, along with the hierarchies which differentiate and legitimize movements. Knowing this, we *may* establish a sense of responsibility and commitment, especially towards migrants on other levels of the hierarchy who, even now, are differentiated or cast aside. However, the near invisibility of this structural issue—by which we mean the practices of differentiation which permeate asylum and refugee policies—presents an uncomfortable home truth, namely that the racialization of migration according to origins and routes, becomes *normal*.

Previous publications have already underlined the *differential humanities* implied when approaching politics of refuge and asylum in the EU (De Conninck 2023; Musyimi

2023 Alsbeti 2022; Zarkov 2022; Costello and Foster 2022). Using a discourse analysis methodology, a recent thesis deepens on the different responses of the EU to refugee's movement in 2015 and 2022 (Prideaux de Lacy 2023). Approaching EU, Germany and Sweden immigration reports and newspapers, the author concludes that "EU values are utilized to alienate outsiders, and therefore not universally applied to all refugees" (2023, 49). Changes in the use of languages (from 2015 refugee to 2022 humanitarian crises), or the emphasis in 2015 in connections with EU threats against member states of the origin non-EU countries are part of the concluding findings of this work, that underlines the EU identity politics (Prideaux de Lacy 2023) embedded in the *normalization* of the 2022 mobilities geopolitical status.

The immobilization of war related refugees in the past under the paradigm of the containment of mobility has been superseded in the case of Russia-Ukraine war related mobilities. The exceptionality of the 2015 war mobilities and the normalization of war mobilities in 2022 stresses not only the inequalities in solidarity (Carrera *et al.*, 2022), but also a biased requalification of movements that defines what is *inside* and *outside* of the political community, performing its geopolitical limits.

The Numbers and Perceptions Game: what next?

Little remains to be said about the role of movement and migration in society. Institutions, research institutes and academics have all expounded on its impact in various terms depending on the context in question: economic and consumerist terms in contexts of limited growth; demographic terms when discussing ageing societies; and in terms of care in contexts of growing dependent groups. The impact of migrant remittances on the local and regional economies from which they originate shows the stability of a complex and counter-cyclical system of exchange and circulation of people, goods and money; according to the World Bank, the total amount climbed to 626 billion USD in 2022 (World Bank 2022).

However, divergences between different narratives continue to provide insights that would be worth exploring in bigger depth. A recently published article on immigration in Germany, France, the USA, Italy, the UK and Sweden, which draws on statistical data from a total sample of 24,000 non-immigrant people, suggests that a large part of the debate surrounding immigration is characterized by misinformation and stereotypes, often stemming from anti-immigration political parties and media outlets (Alesina, Miano & Stantcheva 2022).

The research therefore focuses on the discrepancy between perceptions and facts: with the exception of Sweden, the people interviewed assumed that the proportion of immigrants in their country was at least double the actual amount. They also had incorrect perceptions of where immigrants had come from, believed that they depend more on state Welfare than they really do, and that they are less educated and have a higher rate of unemployment than the corresponding figures show. The article concludes that narratives surrounding the politicization of mobilities and

movements hold greater sway over people's opinion than data. In light of this, now may well be the time to think about other narratives which make it possible to put movement at the center of how society is formed, without romanticizing, chasing, victimizing or coddling migrant experiences, but rather seeing them as a cornerstone of what defines the social formations and change. Perhaps it is an interesting route to reflect on the diverse dimensions and voices in the making of the geopolitics of global change, approaching the reproduction of institutional and non-institutional rhetoric that links (im) mobility to security, the practices and processes that legitimize certain forms of migration, the racialization of insecurity and hierarchies of movements, the sidelining and hiding of the mobile and the migrant, or the possibilities of unconventional dwelling spaces for people in movement. Imaginably we may question how all these elements have come to be as part of what is assumed and reproduced as *normal*.

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